

Generation of Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK293 wild type- overexpression cell lines

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Protocol description

Protocol for the generation of isogenic wildtype (WT) overexpression (OE) Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK 293 cell line pools via transfection.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK 293 kit (ThermoFisher, A15008)▪ Modified (HA-Strep-tagged) pJTI™ R4 CMV-TO MCS pA Vector with inserted cDNA
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Lipofectamine 3000 (ThermoFisher, L3000001)▪ Blasticidin (Invivogen, ant-bl-5b)▪ Opti-MEM (ThermoFisher, 31985070)▪ Geneticin/G418 (Sigma-Aldrich, A1720)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sterile tissue culture hood

Reagents setup

50 mg/ml stock solution of Geneticin

Dissolve 5 g of Geneticin in 100 ml of ddH₂O and sterilize through a 0.22- μ m filter and store at 4°C.

Procedure

▪ Transfection - Day 1

1. Seed JumpIN T-Rex HEK293 cells in 1 ml at a density of 90000 cells/well on a 24 well plate

▪ Transfection - Day 2

2. Check JumpIN T-Rex HEK293 cells (should be 50-70% confluent)
3. Prepare transfection reagents:
4. Lipofectamine MM (scale up according to planned transfections, add 10% extra)

	μ l per reaction
Optimem	42.9
Lipofectamine 3000	2.1
Total volume	45

5. Let the Lipofectamine MM incubate for 10 min at RT
6. DNA MasterMix (MM) (scale up according to planned transfections, add 10% extra)

	µl per reaction
Optimem	29.7
R4 Integrase (100 ng/ul)	4.5
P3000 Reagent	1.8
Total volume	36

7. Pipette 36 µl of DNA MM per reaction into clean PCR strips or plates
 8. Add 9 µl of overexpression plasmid (concentration: 50-100 ng/µl) to 36 µl of DNA MM
 9. Mix 45 µl of Lipofectamine MM per reaction with each DNA MM
 10. Incubate at RT for 5-15 minutes
 11. Add 60 µl of mix to cells (keep pipette tips in medium while dispensing but do not touch the bottom of the wells)
- **Transfection - Day 3**
 12. Change medium to 1 ml of fresh DMEM
 - **Transfection - Day 4**
 13. Transfer the cells to a 6 well plate.
 - **Transfection - Day 5**
 14. Change medium to selection medium containing 2 mg/ml Geneticin.
 - **Transfection - Day 5-20**
 15. Monitor the cells while on selection, change medium every 2-3 days by pipetting very carefully to avoid detaching the cells
 16. Once the selection control has died completely, change back to medium without antibiotics
 17. Allow the emerging colonies to grow for a few days before trypsinizing them
 18. Transfer the cells to a 10 cm plate once they are near confluency
 19. Freeze the cells once they have reached >80% density
 20. Before an experiment, select the cells with 2 mg/ml Geneticin and 5 µg/ml Blasticidin to ensure proper induction of the transgene.

<http://re-solute.eu>
SP0000-7_v2.0

Additional notes

Data/reagent availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/reagents>

References

Cell lines were used in several [RESOLUTE/REsolution publications](#).

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.